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From Climatic Hazards to Systemic Vulnerabilities: Evolving Perceptions of Climate Risk in Norway's Renewable Energy Sector

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Abstract

The impacts of climate change are becoming increasingly apparent, yet the influence of transitioning to a renewable, weather-dependent energy system on risk remains insufficiently examined. This article addresses this gap with three empirical case studies, including interviews and a sectoral survey, which explore how stakeholders in Norway's renewable energy sector perceive and interpret climate risk. While previous research on the effects of climate change on the energy system often predicts positive outcomes for production and demand, especially in Northern Europe, our findings highlight growing concerns about increasing risks. Firstly, there is an acknowledgement that previous assessments overestimated benefits such as reduced heating during warmer seasons and increased hydropower, while simultaneously underestimating hazards from extreme weather events and other threats. Secondly, it has become apparent that vulnerabilities driven by societal changes, in combination with climate change, influence climate risk. The study suggests that transitioning to a renewable energy system may introduce new vulnerabilities, as exemplified by the European energy crisis, which highlights how climatic and non-climatic factors collectively contribute to increasing energy prices and concerns about energy security. These insights enhance our understanding of climate risk in renewable energy systems and highlight the significance of integrated adaptation and governance strategies in creating resilient, low-risk energy futures.

Keywords: Renewable energy system, climate risk, hazards, vulnerability, climate risk perception

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1 Introduction

The transition to a clean and sustainable energy system presents several challenges, as it must be environmentally sustainable, energy secure, and energy equitable. The primary driver of the transition is the aim of reducing global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 100%, in principle, to achieve the 1.5–2 °C goal outlined in the Paris Agreement [1]. To achieve this goal, a global renewable energy share of at least 60% is required by 2050, with even higher targets projected for 2100 [2]. This transition, however, will lead to a system that is increasingly weather-dependent and therefore more exposed to climate-related hazards such as heatwaves, droughts, and periods of low wind and solar generation [3, 4], which can, in worst-case scenarios, result in increased energy prices or power outages.

The European energy crisis of 2021–2022 provides a salient example of how climatic factors can interact with non-climatic drivers to destabilise energy systems and cause sharp price increases (Figure 1). The crisis unfolded as Russian gas supplies decreased, prices soared, and geopolitical tensions over the war in Ukraine intensified [5]. Heatwaves drove up demand while low wind reduced generation [6]. At the same time, maintenance shutdowns at French nuclear plants and drought in Norway and Sweden further strained the system. Norway’s hydropower reservoirs, holding half of Europe’s storage, were critical in balancing supply [5, 7, 8].

Figure 1. Household electricity prices, excluding taxes and levies (€/kWh), in Norway and the EU from 2018 to 2024. Graph A illustrates the European energy crisis of 2021–2022, highlighting key events which affected electricity prices. Graph B offers a long-term context (2008–2024) [9].

The energy sector's engagement in the climate change debate has primarily focused on reducing GHG emissions by increasing renewable energy production, with less attention given to the potential climate risks associated with transitioning to a fully renewable energy system [10, 11]. Until recently, the prevailing view within the renewable energy sector was that climate change would be largely favourable, with production from weather-dependent sources expected to increase (particularly hydropower in Norway), while rising temperatures would reduce heating demand in northern latitudes [12-16]. However, more recent studies suggest that the assumed positive effects may be offset by adverse climatic impacts, including extreme weather events and slow-onset processes such as sea-level rise [17-19]. At the same time, other studies highlight that climate risk in a renewable energy system is not only shaped by hazards (e.g., sea-level rise, flooding, drought, extreme weather events) but also by exposure and vulnerability, including political, social, and infrastructural conditions [3, 11, 20-23]. This aligns with the climate risk framework of the IPCC, where climate risk is determined by the interaction of three core determinants: hazard, vulnerability, and exposure [24-26].

Another gap concerns the limited attention to perceptions of climate risk among energy system actors. While studies on risk perception have explored public and expert attitudes towards renewable technologies, energy infrastructure, energy policy, and the energy transition [27-31], far fewer studies analyse how energy sector stakeholders themselves conceptualise and work with climate risk [23, 32]. Among the limited existing work, Gerlak et al. [32] found that less attention is paid to assessments of risk, stakeholder engagement, and cross-sectoral collaboration in climate risk management in the broader literature on the electricity sector. Juhola et al. [23] found that renewable energy companies primarily account for direct physical risks and transition risks but pay little regard to more systemic and complex risks, such as cross-border impacts or cascading risks. Both papers identify that despite the electric utility industry [32] and the renewable energy sector [23] being key players in the climate change arena and highly vulnerable to its impacts, their current climate risk management practices are fragmented and often fall short.

Norway provides a crucial case for examining these dynamics. With hydropower reservoirs holding half of Europe's total storage capacity [8], the country plays a key role in balancing supply across interconnected European markets. Simultaneously, Norway's heavy dependence on hydropower, increasing electrification, and interdependence with European energy flows heighten exposure to climatic variability and systemic shocks [11]. The 2021–2022 energy crisis, along with the 2023 extreme weather event, Storm Hans [33], in which a hydropower plant's inadequate emergency planning contributed to severe damage [34], demonstrates both the climatic and non-climatic drivers that can destabilise energy systems. In this context, this article examines how stakeholders in the Norwegian renewable energy sector perceive and interpret climate risks. Using a combination of interviews and survey data to explore the stakeholders' perceptions, we aim to answer the following research questions:

1. How do stakeholders in the Norwegian renewable energy sector perceive climate risk?
2. How do stakeholders understand the interaction between hazards and vulnerabilities in shaping climate risk?
3. Has there been a shift in perception before and after the energy crisis?

To contextualise this study within existing research, Section 2 reviews the climate risk framework and explores how energy system studies address risk, hazard, and vulnerability. Section 3 describes the materials and methods, specifying the case study approach and data collection process. The findings for each case study are presented in Section 4. The implications of these findings are discussed in Section 5. Section 6 concludes the study.

2 Climate risks for the energy system

2.1 Climate risk framework

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines climate risk as the interaction of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, influenced by responses [25, 26]. Hazards refer to climate-related events or trends, such as droughts, floods, or storms. Exposure indicates the assets, values, and services at risk, such as electricity infrastructure or energy security. Vulnerability relates to the system's susceptibility and its limited capacity to cope, arising from both technical and societal factors [35]. Responses, in turn, reflect how actors anticipate, perceive, and address risks through governance and adaptation [26].

This framework emphasises that risks are not solely determined by hazards or climate indices, but also by how society organises infrastructure, governance, and values. Climate risk can be categorised into various types depending on how it manifests. Transition risks refer to socio-economic and policy uncertainties associated with decarbonisation—such as stranded assets, volatile electricity prices, or disruptive regulatory changes [25]. Physical risk refers to the direct and indirect impacts of climate change on the physical environment. Direct physical risks can occur when extreme weather damages infrastructure, as seen during Storm Arwen in the UK in 2021, which ageleft over one million customers without electricity owing to the collapse of transmission lines [36]. Indirect risks arise when climate change impacts supporting resources; for example, heatwaves and droughts can decrease river flows, thereby limiting the availability of cooling water for French nuclear plants, which leads to significant production restrictions [37]. Recently, studies have increasingly emphasised systemic climate risks that extend beyond isolated hazards [23, 38-40]. Cascading risks occur when local disruptions spread through interdependent systems, as seen in the 2021 Texas blackout, where extreme cold triggered generation losses that cascaded into failures in power, water, and healthcare systems [41]. Transboundary risks occur when climate change impacts cross national borders, for example, through interconnected grids and shared energy markets [38]. Compound risks emerge when multiple hazards occur simultaneously or sequentially, such as “Dunkelflaute” periods of low wind and solar generation coinciding with cold spells in Northern Europe [42, 43]. Together, these categories illustrate the multifaceted and systemic nature of climate risks to energy systems.

2.2 Hazards and opportunities

Numerous studies have explored the impacts of climate change on energy systems. Early research concentrated on mean climate changes and their effects on technology-specific production and distribution, as well as climate-driven shifts in demand. Studies that focus solely on potential future changes in resources, production, or demand

caused by mean climate changes often indicate positive outcomes for Northern Europe (Table 1). As a result, discussions have often emphasised opportunities rather than risks [13, 44]. These findings shaped an optimistic narrative in both research and policy, where climate change was frequently presented as an opportunity for regions with a high share of renewable energy, such as Norway [12, 16, 44].

However, more recent research highlights that such benefits are likely to be offset by climatic extremes, variability, and systemic disruptions. Hazardous events pose significant threats to global energy systems, contributing to more than 30% of power outages from 1965 to 2012 [45]. As climate change and ageing infrastructure continue to present challenges, these disruptions are expected to increase [45]. The European Climate Risk Report highlights that the European energy system is particularly exposed to heat and prolonged droughts, which will increasingly impact energy supplies. Inland and coastal flooding pose significant risks to the continent’s energy infrastructure [46].

Although technology-specific analyses are useful, they also expose the limitations of hazard-focused approaches. They often ignore multi-hazard contexts where risks interact in complex ways. For instance, compound events such as droughts reducing hydropower, just as heatwaves increase cooling demand, can have consequences far greater than the sum of individual impacts [47]. Without considering such dynamics, risk assessments may underestimate the true scale of challenges faced by electricity systems.

Table 1. Summarises the potential effects of climate change on power generation, demand, and infrastructure in Northern Europe.

Component	Possible effects of climate change	References
Changes in production		
Hydropower	Increase in production due to higher precipitation in Northern Europe. Projected increase between 20% and 25%.	[12, 14, 16, 48, 49]
Wind Power	Potential increase in generation by the end of the 21st century due to more favourable wind conditions.	[12, 48]
Solar Power	Less confident outlook, potential reductions in production due to increased cloud cover.	[12, 49, 50]
Bioenergy	Increase in production due to higher yields from resources allocated to bioenergy production.	[13, 49]
Changes in demand		
Heating	Decrease in demand due to rising temperatures in Northern Europe.	[12, 44, 50-52]
Cooling	Increase in demand due to rising temperatures in Northern Europe.	[12, 44, 50-52]
Impacts on infrastructure		
Electricity network and power plants	Hazards such as more frequent extreme weather events, flooding, droughts, wildfires, and sea-level rise could lead to disruptions in the distribution and supply of electricity.	[15, 18, 19, 32, 53-55]

2.3 Vulnerability and exposure

While hazards act as triggers of disruption, vulnerability and exposure shape the magnitude and distribution of impacts. Strictly defined, vulnerability is often viewed in technical terms: the strength of infrastructure design, the reliability of grid components, or the capacity for redundancy and maintenance [56]. In an energy system, vulnerability stems from various internal factors, including production, infrastructure, and distribution. It is usually categorised into technical (such as equipment and ageing infrastructure), human (like personnel responsible for operation and maintenance), and organisational factors (including system planning). Important considerations involve infrastructure location (e.g., placement of generators, above or underground grid systems), material choices (e.g., switching from wood to steel for grid parts), system design (e.g., generators), planning and operational optimisation, and the skill level of workers performing maintenance, upgrades, and repairs [56-58].

Yet a purely technical understanding underestimates the systemic nature of vulnerability. To fully understand and mitigate climate risks, vulnerability must be seen as a dynamic, context-specific phenomenon shaped by an interplay of environmental, social, economic, and political factors [20, 22, 59-61]. Aall et al. [11] highlight the need to extend the research agenda to include the interconnections between hazards and vulnerabilities, as well as how energy transition policies themselves can create new forms of vulnerability. The effort to balance demand and supply in weather-dependent and more volatile production will become increasingly challenging, as electricity demand is expected to rise in sectors such as heating, transportation, and industry to meet emission reduction targets set by climate policies. This necessitates increased production and infrastructure to provide stable, clean, and affordable electricity, requiring additional resources for upgrading, maintaining, and repairing the infrastructure. Broader societal changes, particularly population growth, globalisation, and intensifying climate change impacts, amplify these challenges [11, 46, 62-64]. Blake et al. [64] illustrate this point in their assessment of Great Britain's power transmission and distribution systems, concluding that the indirect effects of climate change—particularly those stemming from decarbonisation policies—are likely to outweigh direct climatic impacts. The transition to a fully decarbonised system, they argue, will fundamentally reshape the generation mix, load profiles, and demand patterns as electricity replaces fossil fuels in heating and transport, thereby introducing new systemic vulnerabilities alongside climate-related ones.

Climate risk assessments often adopt a narrow view of exposure, concentrating on physical assets such as power plants and transmission lines situated near climate hazards [15, 18, 19]. This perspective primarily considers technological sensitivity, such as hydropower or transmission grids, in relation to climate change [15, 55]. While such analyses offer valuable insights into climate impacts on specific assets or technologies, they tend to frame exposure in technical rather than systemic terms. Nonetheless, exposure also encompasses systemic interdependencies among electricity, water, transportation, and information systems, where disruptions can cascade across sectors [53, 54]. Particularly in highly electrified societies, neglecting these linkages risks underestimating climate risks and overlooking how local events can influence broader networks.

2.4 Response, perception, and gaps

While the above three drivers of climate risk (hazard, exposure, and vulnerability) are clearly defined by the IPCC [65], this is not yet the case for the fourth driver, response. However, the official guidance for IPCC authors involved in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report also includes a discussion of this fourth driver [25]. Response encompasses both mitigating and adapting to climate change, as well as the potential for unintended negative effects of responses that may increase climate risks. Response as a risk driver is thus linked to the discourse of maladaptation and (although the term is not used by the IPCC) the logical parallel concept of mal-mitigation. The contribution of adaptation response to reducing climate risk has therefore been omitted so far, which may intuitively seem illogical. In what is probably the first international attempt to establish an indicator-based system for risk-ranking municipalities based on their relative level of physical climate risks, applied in Norway, the response has been parameterised exclusively as measures designed to reduce climate risk [66]. However, since the approach to specifically and practically addressing response remains under development, we have decided to adhere to the original three-factor risk driver model of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, in which we consider the phenomenon of mal-mitigation as a climate vulnerability - that is, the potential that the transition towards a fully renewable energy system could inadvertently increase physical climate risk. Adaptation efforts are thus treated exclusively as a response to physical climate risks, and not as a driver of such risks.

Adaptation responses to climate risks in energy systems have been widely discussed in the literature, yet the emphasis and scope of these studies vary considerably. Much of this work centres on technical and managerial initiatives aimed at strengthening resilience, including protective measures such as flood defences, upgraded grid infrastructure, and diversification of supply portfolios, as well as efforts to enhance modelling capacity and data availability [15, 18, 19, 55]. Demand flexibility, distributed generation, and the integration of smart-grid technologies are also promoted as tools to support both decarbonisation and resilience under extreme weather conditions [67]. Although these measures are vital, they tend to be reactive and heavily dependent on technology. Huddleston et al. [17] note that most adaptations of critical infrastructure remain conceptualised as tangible responses to immediate events (e.g., floods or storms), with far less attention paid to slow-onset processes such as sea-level rise or warming trends.

A common shortcoming in this literature is the limited consideration of interdependencies. Bollinger et al. [53] and Dawson et al. [54] emphasise the deep interconnection of infrastructure systems, which enables disruptions in electricity to cascade into the transport, water, and communication sectors. However, governance arrangements for assessing and managing these cross-sectoral risks remain fragmented, with responsibilities often unclear. Without considering interdependencies, climate risk assessments risk underestimating systemic vulnerabilities and overlooking how local events can propagate through broader socio-technical networks.

At an organisational level, recent studies emphasise the importance of perception in shaping responses. Juhola et al. [23] show that renewable energy companies generally recognise direct physical risks and, to some extent, transition risks, but pay limited attention to systemic, cross-border, or cascading risks. Their adaptation strategies tend to focus on short-term operational concerns rather than fostering long-term systemic resilience. Gerlak et al.

[32] similarly demonstrate that governance logics within the electricity sector influence how risks are framed, affecting which adaptation measures are prioritised. Sobik [68] argues that climate risk increasingly presents as a set of overlapping risks—weather, financial, regulatory, and social—that collectively reshape energy operators’ strategies, underlining the need for integrated risk management.

Broader reviews strengthen these issues. Schaeffer et al. [21] criticise the reliance on historical data and hazard-focused modelling in scenario development, which may produce insufficient results for future planning. [69] also find that, despite numerous studies on climate change impacts, relatively few examine energy systems in a comprehensive or intersectoral manner. This has led to overly segmented insights, with models often neglecting interannual variability, multi-hazard contexts, and compound effects. Mima et al. [52] add that, although demand-side projections, such as reduced heating and increased cooling needs in Northern Europe, are well studied, they rarely incorporate the influence of extreme events, leaving assessments incomplete.

Aall et al. [11] advance this critique by arguing that the prevailing hazard focus in energy system research fails to capture how vulnerabilities and exposures influence risk. They emphasise that the renewable energy transition itself introduces new vulnerabilities, including increased dependence on weather variability and socio-political lock-ins, which are not considered in conventional assessments. More recently, Aall et al. [3] demonstrate that, despite earlier calls, ongoing analyses of the renewable transition continue to overlook vulnerability, exposure, and compound risks. To effectively address these emerging vulnerabilities, future assessments must incorporate a comprehensive understanding of compound risks, ensuring that adaptation and mitigation strategies are robust and resilient to unforeseen challenges [3].

3 Materials and Methods

The study employs an exploratory, multi-method, and multi-case research design because the topic, to investigate how the energy sector perceives climate risk, is currently an underexplored area. Exploratory research focuses on generating new insights and understanding intricate issues in contexts where limited prior research exists [70]. This approach is characterised by its flexibility and diverse methods, which allow researchers to clarify key concepts and identify emerging patterns [71]. Unlike explanatory research designs, which test specific hypotheses, this design facilitates a deeper exploration of real-world perceptions and challenges that cannot be easily controlled or manipulated [70]. To achieve this, the study is organised around and links three Norwegian case studies, carried out at different times, targeting different groups of informants, and using various techniques to select informants and collect data (see Table 2). The first case study was a pre-project for SusRenew (“Creating sustainable renewable energy futures with low climate risks”). The second is a core part of SusRenew, while the third arose from a collaboration between SusRenew and MYRIAD-EU (“Multi-hazard and systemic framework for enhancing risk-informed management and decision-making in the EU”), both of which focus on climate risk in the energy sector. Due to methodological differences, results from the three case studies were synthesised qualitatively rather than combined in a formal quantitative analysis.

Table 2. Overview of case studies.

Case #	Recruitment basis of informants	Selection of informants	Number of informants	Type of interview	Collection of data	Timing of interviews
1	Renewable energy policymakers	Snowball sampling	16	Semi-structured	Direct interview (by phone or digital meeting)	2020
2	Renewable energy companies (production and distribution)	Purposive sampling	49	Structured	Online survey	2023
3	Renewable energy policymakers, stakeholders, and energy producers	Purposive sampling	10	Semi-structured	Direct interview	2023

Case Study 1: Interviews of renewable energy policymaking stakeholders

Case Study 1 is based on 16 semi-structured interviews with Norwegian energy policy actors conducted in 2020 [11]. The interviewees represented a broad range of stakeholders with key roles in debates about the energy system and its operation, including environmental organisations, state-owned infrastructure agencies, regulatory bodies, energy producer interest groups, and a financial support organisation. Selection was based on stakeholder relevance to ongoing debates, using snowball sampling.

The interviews were conducted online due to COVID-19 restrictions and were recorded with the participants' informed consent, in accordance with the guidelines of the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt). The interview guide was developed from existing literature, previous research on climate risk and energy, and input from a joint workshop with stakeholders and the research team. The full guide is available in the supplementary material of Aall et al. [11], while a summary appears in Appendix A of this article.

The guide contained 19 main questions covering topics such as energy transition pathways, climate risks and vulnerabilities (both physical and transition-related), and organisational capacity to manage these risks. Additional items focused on sector-specific risks (e.g., hydropower, wind, bioenergy) and perceptions of whether the transition to renewable energy would increase or decrease climate risks. Coding was performed manually by the research team. Predefined categories—adaptation technologies, risk and vulnerability, and systems for monitoring and evaluation—were used as a starting point, while inductive coding identified emergent themes.

Case Study 2: Survey of representatives from renewable energy companies

This case study draws on an online survey conducted in the spring of 2023 among representatives of Norwegian companies involved in renewable energy production and distribution, carried out within SusRenew (“Creating Sustainable Renewable Energy Futures with Low Climate Risks”). SusRenew focuses on reducing climate risks

associated with Norway's transition to renewable energy. The project examines how climate hazards, exposure, and vulnerability influence the electricity system and investigates adaptation and governance options. The aim is to develop a knowledge base for a sustainable, resilient energy system with minimal climate risk. The survey was implemented using SurveyMonkey and distributed manually by email to more than 100 stakeholders identified through the licensing registry of the Norwegian Water and Energy Directorate (NVE). Judgemental or purposive sampling was used in this case study. In this method, the researcher selects the sample based on whom they consider most suitable for the study. This approach is mainly employed when there are few people in the area of interest, especially when concentrating on a specific field or a small expert group [72, 73]. The questionnaire (see Appendix B) was designed to capture perceptions of both climatic and societal risks to the energy system, with items covering acute events, gradual climate change, and relevant societal drivers. This framing also reflects the backdrop of the 2021–22 energy crisis, which heightened awareness of systemic vulnerabilities in the sector.

A total of 49 respondents completed the survey. Among these, 28 individuals reported responsibility for grid ownership and distribution, whereas 21 reported responsibilities for energy production. Within production, 22 respondents worked with hydropower, 14 with wind power, 7 with solar power, 8 with district heating, and 2 with hydrogen. Respondents typically held senior or technical roles (e.g., directors, grid managers, engineers, sustainability managers), ensuring coverage across both strategic and operational perspectives in the sector.

The survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequency counts, percentages, and cross-tabulations (e.g., comparing production- and distribution-oriented respondents). Results are presented graphically, both as 100% stacked bar charts and as pie charts, to illustrate the distribution of answers. The questionnaire combined multiple-choice items with Likert-scale questions designed to capture perceptions of both climatic and societal risks. While the majority of items were structured on a 7-point scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," some questions employed fewer response categories (e.g., five-point scales). For full wording and response options, see Appendix B. The same dataset has also been used in a master's thesis [74] and published in summary form as three short analyses on the Norwegian Klimamonitor platform (www.klimamonitor.no).

Case Study 3: Group interviews with stakeholders in the energy sector

The third case study is based on anonymous semi-structured, face-to-face group interviews conducted in 2023 with ten participants from renewable-energy policymaking stakeholders and energy producers, as part of MYRIAD-EU (Multi-hazard and sYstemic framework for enhancing Risk-Informed mAnagement and Decision-making in the EU) project. This project focuses on enabling policymakers, decision-makers, and practitioners to develop forward-looking disaster risk management pathways that assess the trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors, hazards, and spatial scales [75]. Scandinavia is one of the project's in-depth case studies, examining synergies and trade-offs between the energy, forestry, and agricultural sectors. To better understand climate risks at the sectoral level, these interviews specifically explored climate risks in Norway's energy sector. As summarised in Table 2, the interviews were face-to-face and organised in a semi-structured format with a guide of key questions (focus group style)[†]. The findings from this case study provide insights into the sector's responses to climate risks

[†] A summary of guiding questions for Case Study 3 is provided in the Appendix. The full set of questions and detailed explanations can be found in van Maanen et al. (2025).

and its perception of vulnerability, highlighting awareness of potential impacts from both environmental and socioeconomic factors.

Comparative analysis across case studies

This study employs a comparative approach to analyse the three case studies on climate risk perceptions. First, we present the results of each case independently to identify the key themes and context-specific findings. Next, we conduct a systematic cross-case comparison. The comparative analysis is structured around our research questions: (1) how stakeholders in the Norwegian electricity sector perceive climate risk; (2) how stakeholders understand the interaction between hazards and vulnerabilities in shaping climate risk; and (3) whether there has been a shift in perceptions before and after the energy crisis.

The cross-case analysis proceeds in two steps. First, we compare how different actors understand and perceive climate risk. This includes distinctions between present and future climate conditions, the relative contributions of climate change compared to societal factors (i.e., vulnerability), and the overall severity of risk perceptions. For example, whether opportunities are considered to offset adverse impacts. Second, we examine temporal differences by assessing how perceptions evolve across the cases, considering both the timing of the energy crisis and methodological differences in data collection.

4 Results

Following the study design, we present the results of each case study separately, and then proceed to a comparison that integrates findings across all cases.

4.1 Case Study 1: How Policymakers Perceive Climate Risk in the Energy Transition

The first case study occurred before the European energy crisis. The interviews, together with a review of current Norwegian policy documents, revealed that Norwegian energy policy actors in 2020 perceived climate risks as the impacts of future climate change on the existing energy system. They failed to consider climate vulnerabilities caused by the ongoing energy transition. Discussions often focused on subsystems and emphasised supply-side perspectives over demand-side considerations. The stakeholders noted that while scaling up renewable energy is politically feasible, phasing out fossil fuels presents greater challenges. They highlighted specific risks, including safety concerns related to hydrogen transport and storage, conflicts over hydropower expansion, and the environmental impacts of wind power development. However, they generally expressed confidence that transitioning to a fully renewable energy system would ultimately lower climate risks, despite a potential short-term increase during the transition.

The stakeholders also viewed societal change and vulnerability through the lens of political processes and resilience. While recognising vulnerabilities in political decision-making, they highlighted Norway's ability to adapt if strong and decisive leadership guides the transition. Civil society actors criticised the production-focused

approach, urging greater emphasis on energy efficiency and consumption reduction to ease the societal burden of the renewable energy transition. When considering the timeframe for climate risks, stakeholders expressed a near-term focus (less than 10 years), expecting increased risks during the transition but predicting a long-term (more than 10 years) decline in risks as Norway moves towards 100% renewable energy. Their planning relied heavily on scenario-based simulations, including hourly models to 2040, which accounted for variables such as temperature, wind, and consumption patterns. Some questioned the reliance on high-emissions scenarios, warning against over-adaptation and potential maladaptation.

While stakeholders acknowledged potential challenges and risks, their perspective tended to emphasise the opportunities offered by the energy transition. They expressed optimism about Norway's capacity to manage and adapt to future risks, citing strong contingency planning and robust forecasting methods. However, there was some scepticism about specific technological solutions, such as carbon capture and storage (CCS), due to financial uncertainties and EU taxonomy restrictions. Overall, the interviewees were confident in their ability to mitigate risks and capitalise on the opportunities linked to the shift to renewable energy. The insights from policymakers in Case Study 1 directly address research question 1, illuminating how climate risk is perceived within Norwegian energy policy frameworks.

4.2 Case Study 2: How Renewable Energy Companies Perceive Hazard, Vulnerability, and Risk

The survey, conducted in the spring of 2023 with 49 respondents (21 from producers, 28 from distributors), examines stakeholder perceptions of climate-related hazards, vulnerabilities, and response efforts—directly addressing research question 1 (How do stakeholders in the Norwegian electricity sector perceive climate risk?) and 2 (How do stakeholders understand the interaction between hazards and vulnerabilities in shaping climate risk?). The questionnaire covered five thematic areas: perceived timing of climate change impacts, potential opportunities, hazard exposure, societal risk drivers, and company-level mitigation efforts (see Appendix B). Results are presented thematically below to align with the structure of the qualitative case studies.

4.2.1 Perceived Timeline for Climate Change Impacts

Respondents were asked when they expect Norwegian society to experience significant negative consequences of climate change. As shown in Figure 2, nearly half (47%) indicated that such consequences are already noticeable, while 35% expected them within the next decade. A smaller group (18%) believed impacts would materialise over the next 20–50 years, and none selected ‘More than 50 years or never’.

Overall, the majority of respondents perceived climate change as an imminent or ongoing challenge rather than a distant future concern.

Figure 2. Perceived timeline for when Norwegian society will experience serious negative consequences of climate change (N = 49).

4.2.2 Potential Opportunities from Climate Change

Respondents were also asked whether certain consequences of climate change could have positive effects on renewable energy production and distribution. Figure 3 shows that a large majority (84%) agreed that increased precipitation could boost hydropower production. Similarly, 61% considered higher outdoor temperatures likely to reduce heating demand.

By contrast, views on bioenergy and wind power opportunities were more divided. For bioenergy, 39% agreed that production could benefit from improved growing conditions, 14% disagreed, and nearly half (47%) remained neutral. Wind power showed a similar split: 51% expressed some level of agreement, while 47% were neutral or disagreed, indicating uncertainty about changing wind conditions.

The statement that climate change might improve the overall security of supply was met with strong scepticism. Only 8% of respondents agreed to any extent, while 78% disagreed.

Overall, while respondents recognised potential opportunities for hydropower and reduced heating demand, they expressed far greater uncertainty regarding wind and bioenergy and largely rejected the idea that climate change would strengthen security of supply.

Figure 3. Perceived opportunities of climate change for renewable energy production and security of supply (N = 49). Responses indicate the level of agreement with five statements: generally more favourable climate conditions could strengthen security of supply, improved growing conditions could enhance bioenergy production, higher outdoor temperatures could decrease heating demand, more favourable wind conditions could increase wind power production, and increased precipitation could boost hydropower production.

4.2.3 Potential Hazards Impacting Electricity Generation and Distribution

Respondents were asked to assess how various climate-related hazards could negatively impact renewable energy production and distribution in Norway.

For production, the highest concerns were linked to landslides/avalanches and flooding, with 71% (n = 35) and 73% (n = 36), respectively, agreeing or strongly agreeing that these could pose risks (Figure 4). Extreme precipitation also caused significant concern, with 76% (n = 37) agreeing to some extent. Conversely, reduced precipitation received mixed feedback: while 43% (n = 21) agreed it would negatively affect production, 30% (n = 15) disagreed or somewhat disagreed, and 27% (n = 14) remained neutral. Reduced snow cover and sea-level rise were perceived as moderately important, with approximately half of the respondents agreeing that they could have a negative impact on production.

Regarding distribution, concerns were even more pronounced. A large majority (82%, n = 40) agreed or strongly agreed that more frequent storm-felling of trees presents a significant risk, making this the most prominent concern

for the grid (Figure 4). Other hazards with high agreement included flooding (84%, n = 41), landslides/avalanches (82%, n = 40), and extreme precipitation as snow (82%, n = 40) or rain (78%, n = 38). Similarly, 74% (n = 36) identified lightning and thunder as threats, and the same percentage also stressed the threat of icing on power lines. Increased humidity and temperature, leading to material deterioration, were noted by a smaller majority (74%, n = 36). At the same time, sea-level rise and storm surge were of lesser concern, with only 50–55% agreement and a relatively high number of neutral responses.

Overall, these findings suggest that respondents regard extreme weather events and acute hazards—particularly flooding, landslides, storms, and tree felling—as the most urgent risks to both production and distribution. In comparison, slow-onset changes such as reduced snow or gradual sea-level rise were viewed as less immediate.

Respondents were asked to specify the time horizon(s) they consider when assessing the impacts of climate change on production and distribution. Since multiple options were allowed, we recorded each respondent’s furthest horizon. The most common upper bound was 2031–2050 (55%), followed by 2021–2030 (14%), 2051–2070 (14%), 2071–2100 (14%), and beyond 2100 (2%). In essence, 69% do not consider impacts beyond 2050, while 31% look to 2051 or later; only one respondent considered impacts beyond 2100. This near-to mid-century emphasis, combined with the hazard rankings above, may explain why acute weather risks are perceived as more immediate threats.

Figure 4. Perceived negative effects of climate-related hazards on renewable energy (A) production and (B) distribution in Norway (N = 49). Bars represent the percentage of respondents selecting each response category on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). Hazards for production include reduced precipitation, reduced snow cover, flooding, landslides/avalanches, storm surge, and sea-level rise. Hazards for distribution include storm-felling of trees, icing on power lines, lightning, and extreme precipitation (such as snow/rain).

4.2.4 The role of societal factors in climate risk perception

Respondents were also asked to identify the societal factors they considered most important for understanding the consequences of climate change on the energy system (Figure 5). Overall, the responses show a strong consensus: across nearly all items, more than 80% of participants agreed or strongly agreed that these factors are essential.

Two factors stood out most clearly: authorities' requirements for security of supply and environmental requirements for new power development. Roughly 86% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that these issues are crucial, with only a small fraction ($\leq 3\%$) remaining neutral or disagreeing. Similarly high levels of agreement were recorded for resources for upgrading the grid (82%) and international climate requirements (82%).

Other factors, such as foreign power demand and exchange, domestic demand levels, and the type of domestic demand, were also considered important, though slightly less so, with around 70–75% agreeing or strongly agreeing. Even for these lower-ranked items, very few respondents expressed disagreement, indicating a general recognition that a wide range of societal dynamics influence how climate change will affect renewable energy.

Overall, stakeholders view regulatory frameworks, infrastructure capacity, and market conditions as key societal factors that influence the sectors' vulnerability and resilience to climate change. Regulatory requirements are considered particularly vital, whereas demand-related factors are seen as less central but still significant in shaping these outcomes.

Figure 5. Perceived importance of societal factors in understanding the consequences of climate change for renewable energy in Norway (N = 41–45). Bars represent the percentage of respondents selecting each category on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree). No respondents selected disagree.

4.2.5 Comparing the Weight Given to Societal and Climate Factors in Climate Impact Assessments

Respondents were also asked how they balance societal and climate factors when assessing the consequences of climate change for renewable energy production and distribution (Figure 6). A majority (57%; n = 28) reported giving equal weight to both climate change and societal change. About one-fifth (20%; n = 10) placed slightly more emphasis on societal factors, while only a small minority (6%; n = 3) considered only climate change. Another 14% (n = 7) leaned slightly more towards climate factors. No respondents indicated that they considered societal change only.

These findings suggest that stakeholders in the renewable energy sector generally recognise the interconnectedness of climate change and societal dynamics. The fact that relatively few respondents perceive climate or societal

factors in isolation may indicate an understanding that the resilience of energy systems depends not only on climate-related factors but also on how societal factors influence the system’s stability.

Figure 6. How respondents weigh societal and climate factors when assessing the consequences of climate change for renewable energy in Norway (N = 49). Bars represent the percentage of respondents selecting each category on a 5-point scale (1= only climate change, 5= only societal change, 3 = climate and societal factors equally)

4.2.6 Overall perceptions of climate change impacts on electricity production and distribution in Norway

Respondents were also asked to evaluate the overall impacts of climate change on renewable energy production and distribution (Figure 7). The results show a variety of opinions. A majority, 43% (n = 21), viewed the impacts mainly as negative. In contrast, 37% (n = 18) considered the effects as mainly or highly positive, while 18% (n = 9) took a neutral position.

Overall, while concerns about negative outcomes were most prevalent, a significant portion of respondents also foresaw potential benefits or adaptation opportunities for the energy sector. This split highlights that stakeholders see climate change not only as a risk but also, for some, as a source of new opportunities (hence Figure 3).

Figure 7. Overall perceptions of climate change impacts on renewable energy production and distribution in Norway (N = 49). Bars display the percentage of respondents by response, from “predominantly negative” to “highly positive,” plus “I don’t know” (n = 1), not shown.

4.2.7 Efforts to reduce the consequences of climate change

Respondents were also asked to what extent they agreed that their company is doing enough to mitigate the impacts of climate change (Figure 8). The responses reveal clear differences between production and distribution companies.

Among producers, most respondents (65%, n = 13) agreed, while an additional 20% (n = 4) somewhat agreed. Only a small minority were neutral (10%, n = 2) or somewhat disagreed (10%, n = 2), and none disagreed. This indicates a general confidence among employees in the production sector that their companies are undertaking sufficient efforts.

In contrast, perceptions in the distribution sector were more varied. About half of the respondents (50%, n = 14) expressed some degree of agreement, either agreeing (n = 5) or somewhat agreeing (n = 9). However, a notable proportion were neutral (18%, n = 5), while others disagreed to varying degrees (n = 5 across the three disagreement categories). This pattern suggests greater scepticism within the distribution sector regarding the adequacy of current measures.

Overall, while producers expressed relatively strong confidence in the companies' climate actions, distributors appeared more divided, with many either uncertain or doubtful about whether current efforts are sufficient.

Figure 8. Perceptions of whether companies are doing enough to reduce the consequences of climate change, divided by sector (N = 49). Bars represent the percentage of respondents in production (n = 21) and distribution (n = 28) who selected each response category on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

4.3 Case Study 3: How Stakeholders Perceive Vulnerabilities to Rising Climate Risk

In the context of the MYRIAD-EU project, anonymous interviews[‡] were conducted in 2023, following the energy crisis, to gain deeper insights into stakeholders' perceptions of hazard combinations, vulnerability characteristics, shifts in exposure, and the synergies and trade-offs associated with disaster risk reduction measures. The stakeholder group comprised Norwegian renewable energy policy-oriented industry associations, Norwegian energy producers, and researchers specialising in energy systems and markets in the Scandinavian region. The findings, which include input from representatives of the energy sector, suggest varied insights into how the Norwegian energy sector perceives its vulnerability to climate risks, highlighting both environmental and socioeconomic factors.

Interviewees consistently emphasised the direct influence of extreme weather events on energy production, particularly when asked about the combined exposure to multiple hazards (see Theme 1 in the Appendix, Summary of Guiding Questions for Case Study 3). Interviewee 1 mentioned, “Our energy production is a direct function of the wind. Extreme high wind, low wind, or turbulence will influence and reduce our wind production... If we have extreme waves, that can damage some of our structures” (Interviewee 1). Interviewee 2 added, “We are seeing a trend that we are getting one-year storms or five-year storms more often than we have had before. If you extrapolate this, it could lead us to an extreme position” (Interviewee 2). These statements indicate that fluctuating and extreme weather conditions are seen as significant risks to the continuity and efficiency of energy production. Concerns regarding the potential impact of rising sea levels on infrastructure were also highlighted.

Along with hazards, changes in socioeconomic and geopolitical contexts were emphasised as contributing factors to the sector’s growing vulnerability (see Themes 3 and 4 in the Appendix, Summary of Guiding Questions for Case Study 3). Interviewee 3 noted, “We are very dependent on the energy price. This big variation makes it difficult for producers to get project financing. No investor likes this because they cannot predict how it would be” (Interviewee 3). Furthermore, the geopolitical situation, especially the war in Ukraine, has worsened supply chain problems. As Interviewee 4 states, “The price of solar panels was going down, but with the war, the price went up. It’s about supply and production” (Interviewee 4).

The fact that stakeholders in the energy sector actively acknowledge vulnerabilities linked to climate risks may indicate a broader shift in perception, moving beyond traditional concerns such as market stability and regulatory uncertainty. Their awareness of environmental threats, alongside financial and geopolitical factors, suggests a growing recognition of climate change as a systemic risk rather than an isolated environmental issue. This shift underscores the increasing need for integrated risk governance that bridges climate adaptation, economic resilience, and infrastructure planning to address the evolving landscape of vulnerabilities better.

[‡] We do not disclose names, company affiliations or other identifying details of participants.

5 Discussion

This study aimed to investigate how stakeholders in Norway's renewable energy sector perceive climate risk. The main focus of the energy transition has been on reducing emissions in energy systems by shifting to renewable energy [23]. Previous research has primarily examined how climate change will affect power production [49], as well as the preferences of experts and the public regarding energy-technology choices in terms of security of supply, environmental protection, and achieving the energy transition [18, 28, 76, 77]. However, understanding how the sector perceives and interprets climate risks will be vital for maintaining a stable and resilient system, as well as for guiding sectoral responses and adaptation [11, 21, 23]. This paper presents three case studies based on interviews with various stakeholders in Norway's energy sector, aiming to understand how stakeholders perceive climate risk (RQ1) and their perceptions of the relationship between climate hazards and vulnerability (RQ2). Lastly, it examines whether perspectives have shifted between Case Study 1 (2020) and Case Studies 2 and 3 (2023), given the energy crisis that occurred in the interim (RQ3).

Across all three case studies, stakeholders recognise climate risk as having a detrimental effect on the electricity system. However, their views differ on how they evaluate the severity of climate risks and whether potential opportunities from climate change, such as increased power production, will outweigh or even exceed the risks. In Case Study 1 (2020), stakeholders focused more on transition risks than physical climate risks. Stakeholders anticipated a short-term increase in climate risk but believed that the energy transition would eventually reduce risks in the long term. Nonetheless, they acknowledged that extreme weather events could harm infrastructure, especially the distribution network. Stakeholders in Case Study 2 (2023) expect increased power production due to more favourable climate conditions, particularly from hydropower and wind power, but perceive a deterioration in the security of supply. Stakeholders in Case Studies 2 and 3 (both 2023) were particularly concerned about the increasing frequency of extreme weather events and rising sea levels, as well as how these factors would strain the production and distribution infrastructure. By contrast, stakeholders in Case Study 2 showed more uncertainty about the overall effects of climate change on the electricity system, whether beneficial or detrimental, compared to those in Case Study 1. Taken together, the three cases emphasise not only the variation in how risks are perceived but also, beyond hazards, the societal and institutional contexts in which risks are embedded.

Accordingly, our findings suggest that climate risk perception is shaped not only by how climate change influences hazards but also by how the transition to a fully renewable system may increase vulnerabilities (RQ2). Firstly, stakeholders in Case Studies 2 and 3 emphasised the importance of considering societal factors, such as environmental, geopolitical, economic, and institutional elements, as part of the climate risk assessment. Case Study 3 specifically highlights geopolitical aspects, particularly the impact of the war in Ukraine on energy prices and security of supply. The war intensified concerns about the stability of energy markets, underscoring the need to consider climate risk alongside broader global issues [7]. Secondly, more than half of the participants in Case Study 2 considered hazards and vulnerabilities to be equally important in their planning processes. As seen in Case Study 1, overall awareness of vulnerability was mainly linked to political regulation as a crucial aspect of managing the transition in the energy system. They generally focused on specific subsystems or technologies rather than the entire system and its interconnectedness with other systems. Therefore, there is a strong emphasis on contingency

planning and reliable forecasting systems to enhance resilience. This approach aligns with resilience-oriented strategies that prioritise the capacity of individual components to recover from disruptions [56, 58]. These differences reflect the variety of viewpoints among actors and cases.

The contrasting perceptions of climate risk across the three case studies may indicate a gradual shift in how stakeholders in the energy sector perceive climate risk. In the first case study, conducted prior to the energy crisis, there was a strong emphasis on long-term benefits from climate change, particularly in terms of increased hydropower potential. This perspective aligns with prevailing expectations in Northern Europe that climate change could bring regional advantages to electricity production [12, 14]. However, this optimism appeared more tempered in the two subsequent case studies conducted after the energy crisis. Although opportunities for increased production are still recognised, concerns regarding energy security, supply instability, and the combined impacts of hazards and vulnerabilities are more prominent. This suggests a possible broadening of the risk lens, though it remains uncertain whether this reflects a deeper structural change in thinking or a temporary response to recent shocks. The recent energy crisis may have influenced this shift, as it sparked an ongoing discussion regarding the future development of electricity prices in Norway, considering the energy transition, interconnections with other countries, security of supply, and the slow progress in developing new renewable production and distribution networks.

These findings corroborate and refine existing research. As identified by Juhola et al. [23], companies tend to focus on immediate, physical risks while keeping assessments short-term. This is reflected in our material: across Case Studies 2 and 3, concerns about extreme weather events (e.g., flooding, landslides, storms) are more prominent than slow-onset risks (e.g., sea-level rise), and in Case Study 2 most respondents consider the timeframe up to mid-century (to about 2050) rather than beyond, reinforcing a short-term, operational outlook [23]. In line with Gerlak et al. [32], this hazard-focused approach, along with diverse priorities among respondent groups, indicates fragmented practices and limited cross-sector coordination, highlighting the need to address these gaps through integrated risk governance.

Furthermore, our findings challenge the earlier optimism that renewable-based electricity systems in Northern Europe might benefit from climate change (more hydropower, stronger winds, lower heating needs) [12-14, 16, 48, 49, 51, 52], revealing that stakeholders now expect issues related to security of supply and grid fragility, consistent with recent studies showing that mean changes in climate indices can be offset by extremes, variability, and slow-onset changes [17, 19, 21, 46]. The focus of the energy transition should extend beyond simply reducing emissions to include adaptation strategies, emphasising the importance of avoiding maladaptation or malmitigation by addressing systemic vulnerabilities in renewable energy systems, often caused by a lack of a comprehensive view of the entire energy system [3, 32]. If these insights are adopted, energy sector adaptation should extend beyond disaster risk management, such as flood or landslide preparedness, to address fundamental issues related to energy demand, consumption, and security. Additionally, tackling more complex risks, such as compound and cascading risks [23], is essential. For Norway, which already has a highly renewable electricity system, these findings suggest that systemic vulnerabilities linked to weather-dependent generation and high levels

of electrification remain a current concern. Consequently, other countries moving towards large-scale electrification may face similar challenges in the future.

While our findings align with prior research and developments in climate-risk frameworks, it is crucial to acknowledge several limitations. Differences among the three case studies may have affected the results. The methodologies used (open-ended interviews and surveys) offer in-depth insights but can yield varied perspectives, depending on the question phrasing and stakeholder roles. The purposive sampling approach, chosen for its relevance and expertise rather than representativeness, limits generalisability to the Norwegian energy sector [78]. Nevertheless, this approach was suitable for the exploratory aim, as it facilitated stakeholder engagement. Although we observed a changed understanding of vulnerability, it remains unclear whether this reflects genuine perceptual shifts or may result from methodological and contextual variations.

6 Conclusion

The energy transition is essential for reducing global GHG emissions and combating climate change, but transitioning to renewable energy faces challenges such as weather dependence, climate impacts on supply and demand, and infrastructure requirements. Recent events, like the 2021–2022 European energy crisis, highlight how both climatic and non-climatic factors increase risks. Understanding these risks is vital. The perceptions of risk among Norwegian stakeholders have evolved over time. Meanwhile, some believed that renewables would lessen climate risks and strengthen Norway's energy independence. However, there is now a growing realisation that climate change can threaten the security of supply. Understanding hazards and vulnerabilities is crucial for a resilient and sustainable energy transition. These insights improve our understanding of climate risks within renewable energy systems and emphasise the need for integrated adaptation and governance strategies to develop resilient, low-risk energy futures. We need to improve climate risk predictions through long-term future projections by viewing the energy system holistically and including hazard, vulnerability, and exposure assessments to ensure a resilient and low-risk energy future.

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Appendix A: Summary of interview guide in Case Study 1

Adapted from: Aall, C., Wanvik, T. I., & Dale, B. (2022). Climate risk perceptions in the Norwegian renewable energy sector. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 14(4), 1047–1061. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-21-0138.1> © American Meteorological Society. Used with permission.

The interview guide covered the following themes:

1. Energy transition pathways – suitable energy sources to replace Norway’s current energy mix; expected speed of transition.
2. Climate risks and vulnerabilities – whether a 100% renewable system would increase or reduce climate risk; types of vulnerabilities foreseen.
3. Risk assessments – where respondents’ organisations had assessed climate or transition risks; barriers to such assessments.
4. Types of climate impacts – importance of understanding impacts of:
 - a. Acute events (e.g., floods, storms, landslides).
 - b. Slow-onset changes (e.g., rising temperatures, drought, sea-level rise).
5. Sector-specific vulnerabilities – which energy sources (hydropower, wind, solar, bioenergy, etc.) require further risk and vulnerability mapping?
6. Societal and policy uncertainties – implications of changes in export patterns, demand profiles, carbon capture deployment, and speed of decarbonisation across sectors.
7. Future knowledge and measures – planned studies or measures to increase knowledge of climate risk; perceived barriers to knowledge development.
8. Final reflections – open-ended input on issues not covered by the structured questions.

Appendix B: The questionnaire for Case Study 2

Introduction text:

What is the survey about?

We are gathering knowledge and perspectives within the energy sector on how anticipated climate changes towards 2100 might influence the production and distribution of renewable energy in Norway.

The survey is limited to representatives of companies involved in the production and distribution of energy in Norway. By renewable energy, we refer to energy generated from renewable sources (hydropower, wind power, solar energy, geothermal energy, tidal energy, or bioenergy); that is, not energy from coal, oil, gas, waste, or nuclear power.

This survey forms part of the research project Creating Sustainable Renewable Energy Futures with Low Climate Risks (SusRenew), funded by the Research Council of Norway and led by Western Norway Research Institute. The project runs from 2023 to 2027. The primary question we aim to answer is: How can the Norwegian renewable energy sector achieve the low-emission targets set by the Norwegian authorities for 2050, while simultaneously making the energy system resilient to climate change?

We would be grateful if you could pass this survey on to other relevant respondents.

Background variables

1. What kind of company do you work for? Enter: _____
2. What is your job title? Enter: _____
3. What is your area of responsibility? (Can tick off multiple options):

Alternatives	Yes	No
Energy production		

Energy distribution		
Network provider		
Hydropower		
Wind power		
Other energy sources		
Operation/maintenance		
Planning		
Sale		
Information		
Marketing		
Strategy and management		
Sustainability		
Other (comment)		

4. When do you think that Norwegian society will seriously notice the negative consequences of climate change?

- We notice them now
- The next decade
- In 20–50 years
- In more than 50 years
- Never

5. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following consequences of climate change can positively impact the production and/or distribution of renewable energy in Norway?

Consequence	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither/nor	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Reduced energy use for heating due to higher outdoor temperatures in Norway							
Increased hydropower production due to increased precipitation							
Increased bioenergy production due to more favourable growing conditions							
Increased wind power production due to more favourable wind conditions							
Improved security of supply for electricity due to generally more favourable climate conditions							
Other suggestions (open field)							

6. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following climate factors could have negative effects on renewable energy production in Norway?

Climate factor	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither/nor	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Extreme precipitation							
Reduced precipitation							
Reduced amount of snow							
Flood risk							
Risk of landslides and avalanches							
Storm surge							
Sea-level rise							
Other suggestions (open field)							

7. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following climate factors can negatively impact the distribution of renewable energy in Norway?

Climate factor	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither/nor	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Extreme precipitation (rain)							
Extreme precipitation (snow)							
Greater risk of flooding							
Greater risk of landslides and avalanches							
More storm surge							
Sea-level rise							
More icing on power lines							
More frequent storm felling of trees							
More lightning and thunder							
Increased humidity/temperature (rot and material deterioration)							
Other suggestions (open field)							

8. When your company evaluates the impact of climate factors on the production and distribution of renewable energy, what time horizon do you consider? (Multiple selections possible)

- The next decade, up to 2030
- 2031–2050
- 2051–2070
- 2071–2100
- 2100 onwards

9. Societal factors influencing the outcomes of climate change: To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following societal factors are important to highlight?

Societal factor	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither/nor	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Resources for maintenance of the power grid							
Resources for grid upgrades							
The extent of domestic power demand							
Type of domestic power demand (e.g., electricity vs. bioenergy)							
Energy efficiency among Norwegian power users							
Foreign power exchange							
Foreign power demand							
Authorities' environmental requirements for new power development							
Authorities' requirements for supply security							
Norwegian authorities' requirements for business development							
International climate requirements							
Authorities' requirements for the price of energy							
Other community relationships you want to add (open field)							

10. How much emphasis do you place on assessing societal factors compared to climate factors?

- Only climate change
- More climate than societal factors
- Climate and societal factors equally
- More societal than climate factors
- Only societal changes

11. What do you think the overall consequences of climate change will be for renewable energy production and distribution in Norway in the future?

- Very negative
- Negative
- Neutral
- Positive
- Very positive
- Do not know

12. To what extent do you agree or disagree that your company is doing enough to mitigate the consequences of climate change?

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Slightly disagree
- Neither/nor
- Slightly agree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Appendix C: Summary of Guiding Questions for the Interview in Case Study 3

This section provides a summary of the guiding questions used in the group interview. The questions are grouped by four different themes. For the full set of questions and detailed explanations, see van Maanen et al. [79].

Theme 1: Hazard combinations

- Key hazard combinations in the Scandinavian region and explain why they matter
- Emerging combinations of hazards
- Implications for risk management

Theme 2: Synergies and asynergies of disaster risk reduction measures

- Examples where measures for one hazard reduced risks for others (synergies) or increased risks for others (asynergies).

Theme 3: Vulnerability characteristics

- Important factors shaping vulnerability
- Sectoral differences on vulnerability
- Cases where vulnerability differed from expectation

Theme 4: Change in exposure and vulnerability characteristics

- Examples on shifts in vulnerability/exposure due to socioeconomic changes, prolonged disasters and combined hazards.